

Students dealing with tasks aiming at model- and context-oriented reflections: An explorative investigation

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Generally, reflections on mathematical concepts seem to be important to acquire mathematical knowledge at school. In theoretical works focusing on how mathematical education can contribute to societal participation and active citizenship, model- and context-oriented reflections play an essential role. This paper presents a study in which 8th grade learners were encouraged to perform both types of reflections through selected tasks. By means of interviews, reflection processes at the student level were made accessible. Results from a first, explorative analysis of the interviews are reported.

Introduction: Reflection for mathematical literacy

In this section, the theoretical background of the investigation is presented. Studies and concepts from selected authors will be cited to point out which expectations are associated by the demand for reflection. Within the framework of these concepts some empirical studies have been carried out. A brief look at them shows that there is a gap regarding the learners' individual reflection-behaviors. The present study addresses this gap.

In discourses that specifically deal with a contribution of mathematics education for societal participation and development of society, reflecting plays a particularly important role. In this perspective, reflecting relates not only on mathematical structures, but targets moreover on relations between mathematical concepts and settings in which they are used. In German-speaking countries, discourses about mathematics education for active citizenship relate to the concept of “Bildung” (education) or “Allgemeinbildung” (general education) (Heymann, 2003), whereas in international context such discourses relate to various perspectives of *mathematical literacy* (Jablonka, 2003) or *mathemacy* (e.g., Skovsmose, 1998). For a more detailed description of the German terms “Bildung” and “Allgemeinbildung” and their relations to mathematical literacy, see Vohns (2017, pp. 968–970).

Roland Fischer's approach to “Allgemeinbildung” faces the division of labour in our society. Not everyone can be an expert in every field. Rather, a person is an expert in one field and at the same time a layperson on all the other subjects. For laypeople the capacity of communication with experts, judging and taking decisions for one's own concerns would be crucial. Fischer attributes the preparation for the role of the laypeople to (higher)

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secondary education and deduces that this would require a focus on *basic knowledge* and *reflection* (Fischer, 2001, 2012). In Fischer's scientific surroundings, a number of works have emerged in which his concept was related more concretely to mathematics teaching. These are, in particular, reports on the experiences of teachers who have designed their own lessons on certain contents according to Fischer's concept. In the research project "reflecting in mathematics classrooms" (Schneider, 2019), in which I am involved, the perspective of the researchers is not at the same time that of a teacher; here, discrepancy between the ideal and the reality of reflecting in mathematics classes is focussed and ways of overcoming this gap are developed. In the conceptual definitions of reflecting, Schneider distinguishes four types of reflection, with model- and context-oriented reflection each designating a separate type. The conceptual definitions will be discussed in more detail in the next section, since the investigations shown in this paper will refer to them.

Ole Skovsmose (1998) focusses *mathematical literacy* or *mathemacy* in the light of education to democracy in a technological highly developed society. In such a society *formatting power of mathematics* takes action when reality is built through mathematical concepts and models. Different types of reflection should contribute to become conscious about this formatting power. Skovsmose is the first to outline the types of model- and context-oriented-reflection. He specifies that "a model-oriented reflection has the relationship between mathematics and an extra-mathematical reality as its object" (p. 199). This relationship involves simplifications that become necessary with any modelling, where certain aspects of reality are taken up while others are neglected. Further, such reflections can face the reliability of model-outputs or the validity of a model. In context-oriented-reflection, mathematical models are analysed from a different perspective:

A modelling can, however, also be considered from a more general perspective with a different interest. The guiding questions could be: What is the actual purpose of carrying out the modelling? What, in fact, is the political and social function of applying mathematics to a certain situation? A reflection guided by such questions can be called a *context-oriented reflection*. (Skovsmose, 1998, p. 199)

With model- and context-oriented reflection, he describes two different perspectives for analysing a mathematical model, especially models used in social contexts. Skovsmose carried out various classroom projects in which students were confronted with uses of mathematics in their environment and were encouraged to reflect about these uses on different levels, not only model- and context-oriented ones.

Katja Lengnink's (2005) approach focuses on "a certain level of mathematical literacy, which allows reflecting and assessing mathematical processes important in every day live" (p. 246). For this purpose, she describes four categories of reflection, combining Skovsmose's model- and context-oriented reflection into one category. This is plausible, as these two types of reflection are not so clearly distinguishable from each other when it comes to formulate concrete questions about models for pupils. With Schneider's (2019) specifications, model-oriented reflection is more clearly distinguished from context-oriented reflection, as the latter no longer refers to a specific model for one particular situation, but to a particular mathematical concept which finds application in various situations.

Christian Büscher and Susanne Prediger (2019) face a *reflective side* of Mathematical Literacy and refer to the OECD definition of the PISA Mathematics Framework (p. 198). They conceptualize the process of reflective learning as “Conceptual Activity” according to Vergnaud (p. 203). Based on tasks to *statistical measures* that students work on in groups during an interview, they construct different possible paths of reflective learning. Their tasks invite to model- and context-oriented reflections, although Büscher and Prediger do not distinguish between any different types of reflection; but unlike the studies mentioned above, they investigate reflection processes empirically on the learners’ side.

Preliminary investigation boundaries and research questions

Beside the rich theoretical work on reflection, partly outlined above, there is a gap in empirical work. Büscher and Prediger contribute to filling this gap by examining students’ reflection processes on *statistical measures* in more detail. In the other empirical studies mentioned above, teachers and researchers were one and the same person and encouraged their students to reflect by means of (sometimes) large classroom projects. In the project “Reflecting in mathematics classrooms” (Schneider, 2019), the perspectives of researchers and teachers are separated in personnel. Nevertheless, the focus remains on an entire mathematics class. The research study described here targets more on the learner level. Reflection processes of students are to be investigated on the basis of tasks that can be worked on largely independently of what is happening in the classroom and that are specifically aimed at model- or context-oriented reflections. These two types of reflection are focussed on because they seem to be particularly significant for the goals aimed at in the theoretical conceptions. In Fischer’s terms, a layperson, unlike a mathematical expert, will need to assess the use of mathematics in a particular context and make decisions about it. Outside the mathematics classroom and after school, the lay mathematician is unlikely to encounter situations in which it is important to get to the bottom of inner-mathematical contexts. Rather, it will be important to focus on connections between mathematical models and the situation they are supposed to describe or standardise, as well as to become aware of possible effects that underlie the mathematization of a situation. There is no doubt that knowledge of inner-mathematical relationships is important for this purpose. In the theoretical concepts, transfer is hoped for at the end: a transfer of knowledge that emerges from mathematics-oriented reflection, but especially from model- and context-oriented reflection. In addition, a transfer of the model- and context-oriented reflection *processes* themselves is desirable, since there will be new types of models and situations in which the previously acquired knowledge must be *transferred* to a new topic. In order to take a closer look at the processes of reflection among students, the study is oriented towards the conceptual definitions of the project “Reflecting in mathematics classrooms”:

Reflection (related to the learning of mathematics in school) means thinking about characteristics, connections, relationships, effects or meanings that cannot directly be read [off] from the given fact. (Schneider, 2019, p. 4)

With this definition, the difficulty remains in assessing what cannot be “directly read off from the given fact” by an individual student. If the student already knows about that particular characteristic, connection, effect..., it might be directly readable for him or her. On the other hand, for someone who does not yet know about particular relationships, reflections are probably necessary when it is required to become aware of these relationships. Model-oriented reflection is set as:

Thinking about relations between mathematical concepts and inner-mathematical, but above all extra-mathematical situations. The focus on reflection is on the relationship between mathematics and the world, on thinking about mathematical models, usually of extra-mathematical situations and their fit, limits, effects, implicit assumptions for the concrete inner-mathematical or extra-mathematical situation. (Schneider, 2019, p. 4)

Model-oriented reflection is here referring to a concrete model for one particular situation. In contrast, context-oriented reflection is not related to a model for a particular situation, but to a certain mathematical concept and its effects in different contexts, of our world and society, in which it is used (Schneider, 2019).

The conducted study aims to gain insights about reflection processes on the level of learners, when working on tasks which aim at model- or context-oriented reflections. The following research questions are meant to be addressed: How do students deal with such tasks? Where is model- or context-oriented reflection recognizable? To what extent can different ways in dealing with the task contribute to or prevent requested reflections? Such different ways can be shaped by taking into account aspects of the context, by the use of mathematical knowledge and skills, or by possible conventions from the mathematics classroom. In order to address these questions, I conducted interviews with pairs of 8th grade students.

Investigative approach: Tasks and interviews

In what follows, two concrete tasks are presented, one of which aims at model-oriented reflection, the other at context-oriented reflection in the sense of Schneider’s (2019) definition. Subsequently, it will be outlined how, together with the tasks, reflections and insights into such reflections are intended to be fostered by conducting interviews with pairs of students. In the next section the findings of a first explorative evaluation of the interviews are shown.

Task 1, headed “Baustelle” (construction site) focusses on model-oriented reflection:

Das Bauunternehmen Heeg beschäftigt 60 Arbeiter(innen) auf verschiedenen Baustellen. Am Einfamilienhaus der Winters bauen 3 Arbeiter(innen). Sie werden voraussichtlich in 40 Arbeitstagen mit dem Rohbau fertig sein. Der Sohn der Winters rechnet ein bisschen herum und sagt: „Herr Heeg sollte alle 60 seiner Leute an unserer Baustelle einsetzen, dann wäre unser Rohbau in 2 Tagen fertig.“ Was meint ihr dazu?

The construction company Heeg employs 60 workers on various construction sites. 3 workers are building the Winter’s family home. They expect to finish the shell in 40 working days. The Winter’s son does some calculations and says: “Mr. Heeg should use all 60 of his people on our construction site, then our shell would be finished in 2 days.” What do you think about this?

(Task 1, original wording above, below translated by C.P.)

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Tasks with contexts like this are common in Austrian Textbooks. However, such tasks usually aim at the calculative goal; e.g., how long do x workers need for the construction. The fit of the model or possible limits for the described situation of the task are usually not considered by the questioning of these tasks. If questions about the fit or limits are in principle faded out in classrooms, then the focus on practising calculations can thwart ambitions that, according to Fischer or Lengnink would correspond to a demand for "Allgemeinbildung". At setting this task, students are assumed to have conceptual knowledge and calculation skills related to inverse proportions. The obviously implausible outcome "60 workers – 2 days" should act as a stimulus to take a closer look at this modelling. Finally, the students are asked about their thoughts on this, leaving open a variety of directions for consideration. The relationship between model and modelled situation might focus on the one hand on the limits of modelling, on the other hand also on the extent to which such modelling is generally suitable.

Task 2, headed "Prozente – geht es auch ohne?" (Percentages – dispensables?) aims at context-oriented reflection:

Das mathematische Konzept Prozent (%) wird in vielen verschiedenen Situationen verwendet. Zum Beispiel in folgender Aussage: „Die Wahlbeteiligung in Österreich an der Wahl des europäischen Parlaments 2019 lag bei 59,8%.“ Was wäre, wenn es dieses mathematische Konzept Prozent (%) nicht gäbe?

(Assignment „Prozente – geht es auch ohne?“, original wording)

The mathematical concept of percentages (%) is used in many different situations. For example, in the following statement: "The voter turnout in Austria in the 2019 European Parliament elections was 59.8%." What if this mathematical concept of percentages (%) did not exist?

(Task 2, original wording above, below translated by C.P.)

Percentages are a form of representation for relative frequency. In this respect, they are interchangeable with other forms of representation. However, the concept of relative frequency itself is not interchangeable. Effects of this concept with respect to different contexts can refer on the one hand to the percentage representation, on the other hand to relative frequency itself. The decision to specify an exemplary context in this task was made firstly to provide a broader field of contexts, as the most obvious one for students might be the commercial context, and secondly to indicate a considerable advantage of representations of relative frequency. The context of the election of the European Parliament was chosen, as it took place a few months before the interviews and the comparison of shares in different basic quantities by means of percentages is advantageous here, since EU member states participated with quite different numbers of eligible voters.

The interviews were conducted with pairs of students. Working on a task in the context of a conversation with a classmate should favour a natural and spontaneous exchange about results and thoughts that led to them. The presence of the interviewer provided the opportunity to intervene spontaneously to ask for more detailed explanations or to introduce other perspectives. The tasks themselves may stimulate reflection, but leisure and time must be provided for it. A reflection-stimulating environment can be fostered by not aiming for a

predefined product but being interested in the students' personal reflections. This survey is based on the following features: Students themselves decided who will work together as partners; the interest in the thoughts and individual working processes was emphasised in the introductory phase of the interview; the students were given paper and pencil for notes but were not required to create a written product. The interviews were documented by means of audio recording. The tasks were worked on one after the other. First, each participant received the task for model-oriented-reflection. For the following five minutes, individual work was scheduled to grasp and first deal with the task. Second, the two partners exchanged ideas and worked on the task together; the interviewer intervened as little as possible but asked for explanations of statements or stimulated alternative directions of reflection. Third, the task for context-oriented-reflection was worked on in the same way. At the end, the interviewer asked for a kind of review of the tasks and students' work progress, in terms of affective feelings.

First findings from an explorative analysis of interviews

An initial analysis of nine interviews on the tasks quoted above provides interesting insights into students' handling and reflecting processes. In task 1 (construction side), aspects from the context are considered by all pairs, but play quite different roles in their considerations. That and how differently fruitful such contexts can be taken up for reflections is to be shown here exemplarily on the basis of three different pairs attending the same class (8th grade).

Gina and Hannah (all names changed) reproduced the son's result in using a table, where they carry out the arithmetic operations underlying inverse proportions. Both picked up the improbability of this outcome for the construction site context. They soon noticed a difference in the requirement of this task, compared to their maths lessons. Using different aspects from the context, they implicitly criticised the model, for example, in using the fact that building materials have to dry. In the process, however, they only explicitly referred to the specific result "60 workers – 2 days" and it is not clear to what extent the modelling itself was challenged here:

- 196 Gina: Aber wenn man jetzt z.B. Beton macht. Der muss ja auch noch fest werden.
- 197 Hannah: Ja! Das heißt.
- 198 Gina: (Pause, 1 Sek.) Das heißt, es funktioniert nicht.
- 199 Hannah: Das mit den 2 Tag ist ja (Pause, 1 Sek). Es kann ja, wenn man sagt, okay die brauchen 40 Tage. Aber jetzt nicht, weil so wenig arbeiten, sondern nur weil es trocknen muss und weil sie, keine Ahnung {verschluckt: was noch}.
- 202 Gina: Ja, schon auch weil so wenig arbeiten, oder?
- 203 Hannah: Ja. Ja, auch. Aber ich glaube, dass das normal ist.
- 204 Gina: Ich glaube, dass das mit 3 Leut

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205 Hannah: Dann kann das ja net in 2 Tag fertig sein. Sagen wir mal, sie würden rein theoretisch, sie würden 20 Tage brauchen, wenn sie so, einfach nur weil es so trocken muss und das alles. Dann geht das ja auch mit 60 Leuten nicht in 2 Tag, nur weil die jetzt zu 60 sind.

(Original wording above, translated by C.P. below)

196 Gina: But if you make concrete now, for example. It still has to harden.

197 Hannah: Yes! That means.

198 Gina: (Pause, 1 sec.) That means it doesn't work.

199 Hannah: The thing with the 2 days is (pause, 1 sec). It can be, if you say, okay they need 40 days. But now not because so few people are working, but only because it must dry and because they, no idea {gulps: what else}.

202 Gina: Yes, but also because there are working so few, right?

203 Hannah: Yes. Yeah, too. But I believe that's normal.

204 Gina: -I believe that the 3 people-

205 Hannah: (at the same time:) -Then it can't be done in 2 days.- Let's say they would, purely theoretically, they would need 20 days, if they, simply because it must dry and all that. Then it can't be done in 2 days with 60 people, just because there are 60 of them now.

A different trend becomes visible with Igor and Janis. Igor noted in the individual work that it would cost more and take longer because of the drying, but they did not address these limitations in relation to the model when they exchanged ideas. Rather, they focussed on inner-mathematical considerations, especially because Igor and Janis followed the son's results in different ways of calculating with Janis rounding the numbers inappropriately.

Kolja and Leo indicated arithmetical operations underlying relations of inverse proportionality, by which the son's result can be reproduced. While Gina and Hannah made productive use of the difference they expressed about the conventions of their mathematics lessons, such conventions seem to be a hindrance for Kolja and Leo. Kolja noted in his individual work that the son's calculation is valid "if all workers work with the same effort", and Leo, when asked, explained to the interviewer in similar terms that inverse proportion applies under this condition. Yet, during their work there was an inhibition to use aspects from the context to evaluate the model. Kolja tried to introduce such aspects into the discussion, but this was rejected by Leo, who pointed out that this would not be suitable for a "mathematical task". The impression that this can be attributed due to conventions of mathematics teaching is reinforced by statements at the end of the processing of this task (see line 270, below) and in the final phase of the interview:

491: Kolja: Wenn man das in der Schularbeit haben würde, so wenn fünf Seiten da sind in einer Stunde, oder in den 50 Minuten halt, dann würde man nicht so lange drüber nachdenken. Man würde das halt einfach ausrechnen.

(Original wording above, translated by C.P. below)

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- 491: Kolja: If one would have that in the test, so if five pages are there to be done within an hour, or within the 50 minutes, then one would not think so long about it. One would simply calculate that.

Only through interventions, the discussion was led to the context of the construction site, and Kolja and Leo emphasised its relation to the model. Leo expressed a very interesting consideration about the modelling done by the son:

- 153: Leo: es stimmt (Pause, 2 Sek) nur, weil zwanzig Mal so viele Leute sind, heißt das nicht, dass sie zwanzig Mal schneller sein, aber
155: Kolja: aber wie soll man sonst aufs Ergebnis kommen?
156: Leo: Mhm (bejahend)
157: Kolja: Ich mein halt
158: Leo: Ich mein, dass sie schneller sind ist klar, aber dass sie nur in zwei Tagen fertig werden, eigentlich wenn man drüber nachdenkt
160: Kolja: Geht das nicht
161: L: Das ist ja nicht die Geschwindigkeit mit zwanzig multipliziert. Sondern nur die Arbeiter.

(Original wording above, translated by C.P. below)

- 153: Leo: it's true (pause, 2 sec) just because there are twenty times as many people doesn't mean that they will be twenty times as fast, but
155: Kolja: but how else should you get a result?
156: Leo: Mhm (affirmative)
157: Kolja: I just mean
158: Leo: I mean it's clear they are faster, but that they are finished in only two days, actually, if one thinks about it
160: Kolja: it's not possible
161: Leo: That is not the speed multiplied by twenty. But only the workers.

This statement, however, did not help them criticise this form of determining the duration of the necessary work as inappropriate. Rather, they agreed that the result determined by the son is not realistic and considered other aspects of the context, ultimately clueless about how to work on the task:

- 252 Leo: Ja es gibt so viele Antwortmöglichkeiten, eigentlich. (Pause, 13 Sek)
253 Kolja: Ich hab gar keine hmh (lächelnd)
254 Leo: Ich weiß auch gar nicht mehr weiter
255 Kolja: Ich hab auch keinen Plan mehr
256 Interviewer: Was findet ihr denn so schwierig? Beim Beantworten?
257 Leo: Ja
258 Kolja: Weil wir nicht wissen, wie wir es begründen sollen
259 Leo: Weil, du hast, wenn du
260 Interviewer: Was, was wollt ihr denn begründen?
261 Kolja: Warums net geht. Weil wir

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- 262 Leo: Ja wir wissen jetzt, dass es eigentlich nicht möglich ist, nur weil man zwanzig Mal so viele Arbeiter hat, dass man zwanzig Mal so schnell ist
- 264 Kolja: Ja
- 265 Leo: Aber, wir wissen jetzt nicht wieso eigentlich
- 266 Kolja: ja
- 267 Leo: was wir da jetzt als Antwort nehmen könnten, wieso das nicht so ist.
- 268 Kolja: wir müssen halt eine Variante finden, wo alles zusammenpasst, so dass es kein Schlupfloch mehr gibt, dann haben wir die richtige. Hmh (lächelnd). Hm (feststellend).
- 270 Leo: Ja wenn das jetzt im Mathematikunterricht gewesen wäre, hätte ich es mit der Tabelle mit der indirekten Proportionalität ausgerechnet

(Original wording above, translated by C.P. below)

- 252 Leo: Yes, there are so many possible answers, actually. (Pause, 13 sec)
- 253 Kolja: I don't have any hmh (smiling).
- 254 Leo: I also don't know any further.
- 255 Kolja: I have no plan either.
- 256 Interviewer: What do you find so difficult? When answering?
- 257 Leo: Yeah
- 258 Kolja: Because we don't know how to justify it.
- 259 Leo: Because, you have, if you
- 260 Interviewer: What, what do you want to justify?
- 261 Kolja: Why it doesn't work. Because we
- 262 Leo: Yes, we know now, that it is actually not possible, just because you have twenty times as many workers, that you are not twenty times as fast.
- 264 Kolja: Yeah
- 265 Leo: But we don't know now why actually.
- 266 Kolja: Yes
- 267 Leo: what we could take as an answer now why that's not the case.
- 268 Kolja: we just have to find a version, where everything fits together, so that there is no more loophole, then we have the right one. Hmh (smiling). Hm (stating).
- 270 Leo: Yes, if this had been in math class, I would have calculated it with the table for indirect proportionality.

Task 2 (Percentages – dispensable?) showed that the context of the election of the European Parliament is still too foreign for 8th grade learners to use it for in-depth reflections. However, students found suitable contexts for themselves to make different considerations, above all using the commercial context with price reductions and value added taxes. This enabled them to work out important aspects of the concept of percentages. Two interview excerpts shall illustrate that below, the first of the two pairs is already familiar to the reader.

During the individual work of Gina and Hanna, Gina suggested that percentages can be used to apply equal shares to different basic quantities. She seemed to have become aware of this only during the individual work phase, where she expressed the idea that a discount

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could also be indicated in absolute numbers. In conversation with Hannah, she found more suitable words for this, compared to the individual written work, and Hannah could follow her explanation well. In addition, Hannah contributed an alternative way of representing relative frequency by means of a fraction:

- 287 Gina: Das ist ja z.B. wenn man jetzt bei Kleidung. Und da sagt man jetzt minus 25 Prozent auf das und das. Dann ist es natürlich egal, ob das Leibl jetzt 10 Euro oder 30 Euro kostet, das sind immer minus 25 Prozent.
- 290 Hannah: Ja.
- 291 Gina: Und das heißt, das ist dann irgendwie schon praktisch, gäh? Weil 100 Prozent kommt ja darauf an von was man jetzt ausgeht.
- 293 Hannah: Ja, sicher. Das ist immer anders.
- 294 Gina: (Pause, 2 Sek) Also Prozent sind schon für was gut. (lacht)
- 295 Hannah: Ja, die sind schon für was gut. Ja, doch das macht schon Sinn. Das ist so ein einheitliches Ding, was man auf Dinge, auf Objekte, übertragen kann. Zum Beispiel eben wenn man so Sachen verkauft, was leichter ist. Weil du kannst net sagen, ich meine du kannst schon, das ist ein Viertel vom Preis weniger.
- 299 Gina: Ja. (Pause, 1 Sek) Aber ist nicht ein Viertel vom Preis, weil das habe ich eben auch da unten irgendwo hingeschrieben, also im Endeffekt läuft das ja wieder aufs Gleiche raus.
- 301 Hannah: Es läuft aufs Gleiche raus. Aber es ist mit Prozent, glaube ich, einfach leichter.
- 302 Gina: (Pause, 2 Sek) Ja, aber so ein Bruch und Prozent hängen ja zusammen. Und eigentlich haben wir die Dezimalzahlen. Glaube ich halt. (lacht)

(Original wording above, translated by C.P. below)

- 287 Gina: That is, for example, if one with clothes now. And there one says now minus 25 percent on this and that. Then, of course, it doesn't matter if the shirt costs 10 euros or 30 euros, it's always minus 25 percent.
- 290 Hannah: Yes.
- 291 Gina: And that means it is somehow practical, isn't it? Because 100 percent depends on what you start out from now.
- 293 Hannah: Yeah, sure. That is always different.
- 294 Gina: (Pause, 2 sec) So percent is really good for something. (laughs)
- 295 Hannah: Yeah, it is really good for something. Yes, that makes sense. That is such a uniform thing, which you can transfer to things, to objects. For example, if one sells stuff or so, which is easier. Because you can't say, I mean you can, that's a quarter off the price.
- 299 Gina: Yes. (Pause, 1 sec) But isn't a quarter of the price, because that's what I just wrote down there somewhere, so in the end it comes back to the same thing.
- 301 Hannah: It comes out to the same. But it's just easier with percent, I believe.

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302 Gina: (Pause, 2 sec) Yes, but a fraction and percent are related. And actually we have the decimal numbers. I believe. (laughs)

Mark's and Nicolò's reflections addressed the fact that looking at a relative share can produce very different perspectives depending on what it refers to:

376 Mark: Oder auch im Sport, wenn sie manchmal so sagen, also das sagen sie nicht, aber rein theoretisch, wenn du sagst jemand ist zwanzig Prozent schneller als wie der vorherige

378 Nicolò: (flüstert) Ja, aber das sagst du net.

379 Mark: Ja, aber jetzt rein theoretisch. Also, im Kopf merkst du nachher schon, der war schon VIEL schneller.

381 Nicolò: Mhm (bejahend).

382 Mark: Als wie wenn du nachher die Zahlen siehst, dass der irgendwie fünf Sekunden schneller war oder so. Wenn du die Prozent hörst, wirkt das natürlich gleich viel mehr. (Pause, 2 Sek) Und ist eben auch bei den Rabatten, dass wenn da steht das ist zehn Prozent, denkst du dir gleich, das ist nicht so wenig. Aber dabei ist das gar nicht so viel.

(Original wording above, translated by C.P. below)

376 Mark: Or also in sports, when they sometimes say things like that, well they don't say that, but purely theoretically, if you say someone is twenty percent faster than the previous one

378 Nicolò: (whispers) Yes, but you don't say that.

379 Mark: Yes, but purely theoretically now. So, in the mind you notice, that was MUCH faster.

381 Nicolò: Mhm (affirmative).

382 Mark: Like when you see the numbers afterwards, that he was somehow five seconds faster or something. When you hear the percentages, of course, it has a much higher impact. (Pause, 2 sec) And it's the same with discounts, that if it says that's ten percent, you immediately think to yourself, that's not little. But in fact it's not that much.

Moreover, the interviews reveal that learners have difficulties with inner-mathematical connections between percentages, fractions, and decimals (see Gina and Hannah, line 302) and that this partly hinders context-oriented considerations.

Summary and outlook

Based on theoretical concepts from the first two sections, the question arose how learners deal with tasks that target specific types of reflection. Through interviews interesting insights to reflection processes emerge on three different aspects.

First, the extra-mathematical context can be differently fruitful for reflections. Depending on how learners are able to deal with it, it can contribute to relevant reflections (such as the drying for Gina and Hannah in task 1, discounts and sports in task 2) or lead to getting lost in reflections of the context while the mathematics gets out of focus. Second, deficient

mathematical knowledge and skills can partly hinder model- and context-oriented reflection. Resulting discussions of inner-mathematical relationships can be quite fruitful, but at the same time the level of model- and context-oriented reflection may be left out (e.g., Igor and Janis). Thirdly, presumed conventions from mathematics classes become visible. A focus on fast and strict processing of clearly solvable tasks may limit the view of mathematical models, as in the case of Leo and Kolja, but Gina and Hannah show that this does not necessarily have to be the case. With regard to task 1, it should be examined whether a formulation that presents the selective result “60 workers - 2 days” less prominently encourages the learners to reflect more on the model as a whole and its limitations.

Overall, the first explorative approach to the analysis of the interviews allows to describe peculiarities that seem to inhibit reflections on the one hand. On the other hand, students conducted a variety of relevant reflections. Further analysis of the interviews should focus more specifically on the task processing as a whole, less at isolated passages for deeper insights regarding model- and context-oriented reflection processes. Follow-up interviews with the same students on other tasks with different mathematical contents are planned. The search is on for model- or context-oriented reflection processes across specific contents and tasks.

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